

Research on Motivation Factors Among Employees in the Social Services System

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Abstract

This study aims to identify key motivator factors influencing individuals' commitment to work in the social services system. Motivation is an extremely significant, and yet complex process. Furthermore, the issue of motivation for employees working outside of business organizations, in so-called "helping" professions, including those in the social work system, needs additional research in our society. For that purpose a survey on factors of motivation of employees in the social services system was created and conducted. This survey is based on the motivation theories which attempt to uncover which factors influence employee motivation – considering their expectations for external rewards, and the internal mindset and values of the individual, as both are considered important, including the theory of Public Service Motivation referring to the specific motivation in non-business organizations and the concept of the Mission Valence. The findings highlight that relationships with colleagues, organizational policies, recognition, and fairness are the dominant motivational factors, confirming the hypothesis that intrinsic motivators outweigh extrinsic incentives.

Keywords:

Work motivation, Social services system, Factors of motivation, Social work

Introduction

Globally, work in social services system is considered low-paid and stressful, despite its benefits to society and, in particular, to clients in difficult situations. According to researchers within the EU, the average career span in social work is eight years, and 73% of social workers experience emotional exhaustion because of their job (Curtis, Moriarty, Netten, 2014). This is a concerning trend but revealing it could lead to improved working conditions and better support for those employed in the sector. Examining the factors that drive motivation among employees in the system is crucial for their long-term retention. The challenging nature of helping professions should be a subject of discussions and research. However such large-scale studies focused on employees in the social services system are lacking in our country.

Literature review

The different personal meanings attributed to labor are best illustrated in the parable of the three workers performing the same task. When asked what they are doing, they each give completely different answers. The first responds that he is cutting stones, the second says he is earning a living, and the third states that he is building a temple (Urbanowicz, 2007). Thus, work or the effort invested in each activity carries multiple meanings and contains various reasons for its execution, depending on the individual.

One of the most common definitions by researchers states that motivation is defined as a force that performs three functions: it energizes or drives people to act, directs behavior toward achieving specific goals, and sustains the efforts put into reaching these goals (Steers, Porter, 1991). On the one hand, understanding motivation implies answering the question "What drives and motivates people to work?". The goal is to identify the main reasons why people start working, put in effort, and continue to do so despite changing circumstances. This requires taking needs into account, with this research perspective being heavily influenced by Abraham Maslow's theory (Maslow, 1987) and developing into specific work-related theories (Alderfer, 1969; Herzberg et al., 1959; McClelland, 1961). These theories are developed as content theories and are static in nature, as they describe the personal foundations for motivation and differences in needs and motives, but do not explain the process of motivation itself and, ultimately, do not answer the question of why some people are more motivated and work harder than others under the same conditions. On the other hand, however, uncovering the needs of the individual is not enough to

explain motivation—people have similar motives and needs that they try to satisfy through work, but at the same time, they put in different efforts and achieve different results in their performance. Therefore, a comprehensive understanding of motivation also requires an answer to the question "How?", i.e., how the process of motivation itself unfolds, and what factors influence this process.

This gradually expands the theoretical approaches for analyzing motivation, with the development of views on the role of expectations and rewards, beliefs and values of the individual, personal choice (Lawler, 1973; Vroom, 1964), the fairness of received rewards and their alignment with the individual's efforts (Adams, 1965), and the characteristics of the job itself (Hackman, Oldham, 1976), all of which have a motivating effect on behavior.

A distinctive feature of many motivation theories is that they are strongly pragmatically oriented and aimed at direct interventions in organizational settings to increase motivation and, consequently, improve job performance. External stimuli often have a quick and strong effect, but rarely a lasting one, unlike internal stimuli, which has a deep and enduring impact because they are inherent to the individual rather than imposed from the outside (Ilinchev, 2012).

Also important in determining the motivations of individuals who choose careers in the government and non-profit sectors despite the potential for more financially lucrative careers in the private sector is understanding of the theory and practice of Public Service Motivation. **Public Service Motivation** is an attribute of government and non-governmental organization employment that explains why individuals have a desire to serve the public and link their personal actions with the overall public interest. Public Service Motivation serves to provide the general public with an idea of what motivates individuals to choose career paths within the public sector as opposed to the private. Mission Valence can be viewed as an employee's perception of the attractiveness or salience of an organization's purpose or social contribution. *Mission Valence* is a concept formulated by Rainey and Steinbauer (1999) that serves to provide a better understanding of what compels an employee to uphold and achieve goals within their organization. Mission Valence enhances the satisfaction that an individual experiences or anticipates receiving from advancing the organizational mission, and in turn, it has the "potential to influence the ability of the organization to recruit, retain, and motivate its employees."(Wright, Bradley E., Moynihan, Donald P., Pandey, Sanjay K., 2012). Mission valence refers to “an employee’s perception of the attractiveness or salience of an organization’s purpose or social contribution” (Wright, Moynihan, & Pandey, 2012).

The specific theories developed in occupational psychology and organizational behavior reveal various aspects of motivation, and it can only be understood if the interaction between them is considered (Kreitner, Kinicki, 1989; Mullins, 1999). Motivation can be likened to a puzzle, and to "assemble the puzzle," all its pieces need to be gathered (Ilieva, 2009).

The subject of this study is the work motivation of employees in the social services system.

The subject of the study is employees working in organizations providing social services.

Research Objectives

This study purpose is to explore what motivates employees to enter the profession and to continue practicing it long-term. The research seeks to identify the internal motives that drive people to work in social work service units, as well as external factors and incentives that influence workplace motivation.

The study's objectives will be achieved through the following tasks:

- Analyzing existing literature on work motivation.
- Constructing a survey to examine various factors and their impact on the motivation of employees in the social services system.
- Conducting a survey among employees in the social services system, using the created questionnaire.
- Performing statistical data analysis.
- Analyzing the results and drawing conclusions.

Methods for Data Analysis

- Descriptive Statistics – mean values, standard deviation.
- Student's t-test – to identify differences in mean values between variables across different measurements.
- Correlation Analysis.

The statistical processing of the results was conducted using the SPSS Statistics 23.0 software package.

METHODOLOGY

The survey on motivation factors among employees in the social services system is based on established theories and models in organizational psychology. These include: Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs (Maslow, 1987), Alderfer’s ERG Theory (Alderfer, 1969), McClelland’s Theory of Achievement Motivation (McClelland, 1961), Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory (Herzberg et al., 1959), Expectancy Theory (Vroom, 1964; Lawler, 1973), Equity Theory – fairness of rewards in relation to individual effort (Adams, 1965), Job Characteristics Model (Hackman & Oldham, 1976), and the theory of Public Service Motivation (Perry & Wise, 1990).

The survey comprises 21 scales with a total of 110 items. To assess motivation effectively, the study is structured into two sections: a value-based evaluation of potential job characteristics and an assessment of their actual presence in the workplace. This methodological approach follows Jonev, S. (Social Psychology, Vol. 5, Sofia, 2004, p. 225). These scales were selected for their established validity in measuring public sector motivation, ensuring alignment with the unique demands of social work professionals. The motivational strength of a specific factor is determined by the interaction between these two components:

- High value perception + high resource availability → Strong motivational impact
- High value perception + low resource availability → Reduced motivational impact
- Low value perception + high resource availability → Reduced motivational impact
- Low value perception + low resource availability → Minimal contribution to motivation

This framework helps assess which factors significantly influence employee motivation within the social services system.

According to the literature analysis the following factors represent key elements influencing employee motivation in the social services system:

Scales	Number of questions
Compensation (Payment)	6
Job Security	5
Relationships with Colleagues	7
Management Style (Direct Management)	11

Organizational Policies	6
Working Conditions	3
Autonomy	4
Opportunities for Growth and Career Advancement	4
Opportunities for Self-Actualization and Learning	3
Utilization of a Variety of Skills in the Workplace	4
Job Content	6
Task Significance and Meaningfulness of Work	8
Ability to Follow Work and Its Results from Start to Finish	2
Power (Authority)	4
Sense of Belonging	7
Responsibility	3
Recognition	7
Achievements	7
Fairness	5
Expectancy (Perceived Reward for Effort),	2
Value of the Mission	6
Respondent details	5

Table 1 Scales in Survey on motivation factors among employees in the social services system

These aspects align with various motivation theories and help determine the factors that drive employees to remain engaged and satisfied in their roles. They represent 21 scales in this survey.

Empirical study is approached with the following working hypotheses.

H1: The more significant factors for motivation would include: job security, positive relationships with colleagues, sense of belonging, direct management style, autonomy at work, the content of the work, the meaningfulness of the work, and the value of the mission.

H2: A minor factor for motivation would be the possession of power in the workplace.

Results

The survey was conducted among 177 individuals from 34 social service organizations. The distribution of the surveyed employees in the social services system by position shows that the largest group consists of social workers, followed by psychologists, occupational therapists, and healthcare workers. The sample includes both specialized professionals and operational staff employed within the social services system. Approximately 86% of the surveyed employees in the system are women. The largest group of participants in the study are between the ages of 41 and 65 (63 %). Around 35% are between 20 and 40 years old. It is concerning that the number of employees under 40 years old is significantly lower. Attracting young and educated professionals, as well as ensuring their long-term retention in the workplace, is one of the challenges in the field of social services.

The largest proportion of respondents in the study have 1 to 5 years of experience in the field, followed by employees with 6 to 10 years of work experience. Despite the higher age of the respondents in the current sample, the proportion of employees with over 10 years of work experience is significantly smaller.

The importance of compensation was perceived as valuable by a large portion of the respondents, while the evaluation of providing such compensation is found in the middle range. Although improving compensation could help increase motivation, it seems that work is not merely a tool or means to earn compensation for the surveyed employees, but likely brings other positive benefits that keep them in the organization. Although compensation plays an important role, it does not stand out as the leading motivation factor but rather contributes to the overall level of job satisfaction. *Job security* as a motivational factor appears to be a moderately attractive factor for employees but not of primary importance, as it does not stand out as a leading motivator. Instead, it contributes to the overall sense of satisfaction and stability. *Relationships with colleagues* on the other hand are identified as one of the most significant factors for employee motivation at the workplace. According to the results, employees value having good relationships with their colleagues, and their high evaluation of actual positive relationships in the organization indicates the motivating power of this factor. Good relationships with colleagues are a strong motivating factor in the work environment, having a significant influence on employee satisfaction and engagement. This factor is followed by the type of direct management within the organization, which seems to have an impact on employee motivation and satisfaction, though not as a leading

factor. Employees indicate that they find the *organization's policies* of high importance. However, there is a moderate to strong discrepancy between the value employees place on adequate organizational policies and their assessment of their actual presence in the organizations. The observed difference suggests that organizational policies are seen as an important factor that can influence employee engagement in work.

Working conditions as a motivational factor within the organization. It seems that employees consider an organized and clean workspace, a technologically equipped workplace, and the availability of necessary physical resources to perform their tasks as significant. The results show that although these provisions matter to employees, they do not stand out as a dominant motivation factor. *Autonomy* at work is valued by employees. It seems to be quite present in the work of many respondents. Still, according to the results, autonomy is of some importance to employees' motivation, though not a decisive factor for significant changes in their perceptions. The results show that the *opportunities for growth and career advancement* are crucial for employee motivation, as the presence or absence of such opportunities can significantly affect their engagement in work and career development. Therefore, opportunities for growth and advancement could be considered a key motivating factor in employee work. *Opportunities for self-actualization and learning* are valued by employees, and such opportunities are present to a certain extent in their organizations. This seems to be a moderately motivating factor for employees at the time of the survey, and improving opportunities for self-actualization and learning could motivate employees further. Still, they are not among the leading factors that significantly impact their motivation. The *opportunity to use a variety of skills at the workplace* seems valuable to the employees surveyed, and according to the answers this factor is quite present in their work. The results show that the use of various skills is of some importance for work motivation, but it is not one of the main factors determining employee engagement. The *content of the work* appears to be a more important factor for employees. They seem motivated by the actual work they do and its content. Nevertheless, the results show that the content of the work has a relatively stable impact on employee motivation, without being a key factor for changes in their perceptions. Regarding the *significance of the task and the meaningfulness of the work*, this factor seems to have a stable influence on employee motivation and satisfaction, although changes in its perception do not have a significant impact on their attitudes toward work. *The possibility of tracking work progress and results* seems relatively significant for the surveyed employees. The chance to see the results of

their work seems important to those who work to support people and improve their social conditions. This factor has a relatively stable significance for motivation and satisfaction at work, and differences in its perception do not substantially influence employee engagement. Next factor is *power* in work, in the form of holding a prestigious and influential job, having authority over the lives of others, the ability to direct others in solving their problems, and the power to make the best decisions for the well-being of clients in the workplace. It seems that the perception of power matters to employees and may influence their motivation and attitudes toward the work environment. Power is rated as a relatively insignificant factor by the surveyed employees and does not play a significant role in organizations. The results show that power has some role in the work environment but does not have a strong or even moderate impact on motivation; it rather remains a secondary factor among others. This is likely due to the ethical framework in the social services system, which should not impose authoritative decisions on service users. On the other hand, the factor of the sense of belonging to the team, organization, and professional community appears to be significant for employees. According to the survey results, employees largely feel a sense of belonging to their team, organization, and professional guidance. This *sense of belonging* is a relatively stable factor that impacts employee motivation and engagement but does not lead to substantial changes in their perceptions across different contexts. It seems that the sense of belonging contributes to overall motivation, but it is not a decisive factor for it. *Responsibility* has a stable impact on employees, but it does not significantly influence their motivation and is not a primary factor in determining their engagement. Therefore, responsibility has a weak influence on motivation and is not a factor that creates significant differences in how employees perceive their work. *Recognition* at work from society, close ones, and clients is rated as valuable and important by employees, although they report receiving such recognition at moderate levels. The results show that recognition is an important factor for motivation and satisfaction, and differences in its perception can significantly influence employee engagement. *Achievements* in the work process are noted as significant by employees. It seems that the importance of demonstrating various skills at work, becoming better specialists, showing competence, and dealing with challenges at work has a relatively stable influence on the surveyed employees in their work. According to the results, increasing opportunities for achievements in work may moderately influence employee motivation. The factor "achievement" has a relatively stable influence on motivation and satisfaction, without leading to significant changes in their perceptions. Fairness in the workplace

or the desired balance between efforts and results, as well as employees' desire to be treated fairly and equally, is seen as an important factor by the participants in the study. Although fairness is subjectively experienced by everyone, the trend is that when employees feel they are treated fairly, it leads to higher motivation. The factor "*fairness*" plays an important role in motivation and satisfaction, and significant differences in its perception can have a strong impact on their engagement and attitudes toward the work environment. Employees' expectation that their efforts at work will be recognized and positively rewarded seems to be of high importance to them, and the results show that this expectation is present at moderate levels in their work at the time of the survey. The factor "*expectations*" is important for employee motivation and satisfaction, and differences in their perception can influence their attitudes and engagement with the work. The *value of the mission* plays a role in employee motivation and engagement, with even small changes in its perception being able to influence their attitude toward work. The results show the value of the mission has a moderate to strong impact on employee motivation. Organizations should prioritize fostering strong workplace relationships and fair recognition practices, as these factors significantly contribute to job satisfaction and retention.

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